

**XIX ASR OXIRI – XX ASR BOSHLARI TURKISTON TARIXIGA OID OLIB
BORILGAN XORIJIY VA MAHALLIY TADQIQOTLAR****Muyiddinov Bekali Bahodir o'g'li**

Buxoro viloyati Osiyo xalqaro universiteti Tarix fani o'qituvchisi.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada XIX asr oxiri – XX asr boshlarida Turkistonda olib borilgan keng ko'lamli o'rganishlarning tadqiqotlarda aks etilishi haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Leon Koshar, Turkiston to'plami, K.P. Kaufman, Sankt-Peterburg, A.A. Semyonov, Muhammad Yusuf Bayoniy, Toshkent, Qo'qon, Buxoro, E. Bulanje, Arminiy Vamberi.

Leon Kosharning "Parij-Buxoro-Samarqand" nomli asari fransuz tadqiqotchisining shaxsiy sayohati va kechinmalari haqida yozilgan bo'lib, unda Buxoro amirligi bozorlari, unda Buxoro va Samarqand madrasalari haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Qayd etilgan memuarlar juda keng qamrovli bo'lib, ular qatorida nemis tilida yozilgan asarlar ham katta hajmga ega.

P. Kuznetsovning "Markaziy Osiyoda sivilizatsiya va tillar kurashi" deb nomlangan mazkur asari mintaqamizga sayyoh ning shaxsiy tadqiqotlari natijasida yaratilgan bo'lib, ikki bo'limdan iborat.

Uning ikkinchi bo'limida, xonliklarning vujudga kelishi, aholisi, ayollar masalasi islom va tasavvuf hamda Markaziy Osiyodagi dunyoviy fanlar holati haqida ma'lumotlar keltiriladi.

Shu bilan birga mamlakatlar etnografiyasi va ruslar bosqini masalalari ham keltirilgan. "Turkiston to'plami"ning to'liq nomi "Turkiston o'lkasi va O'rta Osiyoga tegishli bo'lgan maqola va asarlar to'plami" bo'lib, unga 1867-yilda Turkiston general-gubernatori K.P. Kaufmanning shaxsiy topshirig'i bilan Rossiya imperiyasi boshqaruv apparatini Turkiston o'lkasi hayotiga oid turli xil ma'lumotlari bilan tanishtirib borish maqsadida tashkil etilgan.

Unda asosan rus va xorijiy tillarda Markaziy Osiyo haqida Rossiya va xorijda chop etilgan nashrlar – gazeta, jurnal, kitoblardan parchalar o'rin olgan. O'lkani o'rganish uchun bo'lgan ehtiyoj, undagi tabiiy, iqtisodiy salohiyat, boyliklarning joylashuvini o'rganish, metropoliya sanoati uchun zarur bo'lgan xomashyo manbalarini aniqlash va jamlash – ushbu to'planning tashkil etilishiga asosiy sabab bo'ldi.

Jami 594 jilddan iborat, bugungi kunda Alisher Navoiy nomidagi Milliy kutubxonasida saqlanayotgan "Turkiston to'plami" ning asosiy qismini, ya'ni 1-416-jildlari K.P. Kaufman topshirig'I bilan V. Mejov boshchiligida tuzilgan. To'plam 1867-1887-yillarda Sankt-Peterburg shahrida tuzilgan. 1907-1910-yillarda tuzilgan 417-543-jildlari, 1911-1916-yillarda tuzilgan 544-591-jildlari Toshkentda nashr etilgan. "Turkiston to'plami"ning so'nggi 3 jildi (592-jilddan 594-jildgacha) kutubxonashunos Ye.K. Betger boshchiligida tuzilgan. 1876-yil "Maxsus qo'mita" tashkil etiladi va uning zimmasiga "Turkiston to'plami"ni tartibga solish vazifasi topshiriladi. 1907- yili kuzatuv tarkibiga I.V. Dmitrovskiy, etnograf A.A. Divayev, Turkiston kutubxonasi mudiri I.P. Zikov kiritilib, ular tomonidan 127 ta jild tuziladi. Bu vazifani amalga oshirishda N.V. Dmitrovskiyning xizmatlari katta edi. "Turkiston to'plami"ni yaratish jarayonida gazeta maqolalari qirqib olinib, oq qog'ozlarga yelimlangan, jurnal va kitoblar davriy izchillikda tikib borilgan. Jurnal maqolalarining soni 10 000 dan ortiq bo'lgan. N.V. Dmitrovskiy boshchiligida tuzilgan "Turkiston to'plami" ning 417–543-jildlari V. Mejov tuzgan jildlardan ancha katta farq qilgan. 127 jilddan 81 tasi (64%) gazeta materiallari asosida (bularning ichidan 4 tasi o'zbek va tatar tillarida) tuzilgan. To'plam 1887-yilgacha muntazam tuzilgan va yiliga 20 tadan jild tayyorlangan. 1887-yildan ma'muriyat buyrug'i bilan bu ish 20 yil to'xtab qolgan.

1910-yildan “Turkiston to’plami”ni chop etish uchun yana mablag’lar yetishmay qoladi.

Shu yili N.V. Dmitrovskiy va fot etishi munosabati bilan 1911-yildan to’plamni tuzish mas’uliyati sharqshunos A.A. Semyonov zimmasiga yuklatildi. A.A. Semyonov (1873-1958) boshchiligida 48 ta jild chop etildi. A.A. Semyonov “Turkiston to’plami”ning ushbu jildlariga katta o’zgarishlar kiritdi. Har bir jildga alohida mavzu berildi. 1916-yili A.A. Semyonovni Rossiyaga ketishi munosabati bilan “To’plam” ustidan ishlar tamomila to’xtab qoldi. Sovet davrida “Turkiston to’plami” ustida ishlarni o’lkashunos Ye.K. Betger davom ettirdi. 1939-yili Ye.K. Betger boshchiligida so’nggi 3 ta jild – 592-593-594 jildlar chop etildi.

Muhammad Yusuf Bayoniy tarix faniga – moziy ilmiga ma’rifat va haqiqat chirogi deb qaradi. Bayoniy tarixiy hodisalar g’oyat to’g’ri va ishonchli yozilishini tarbiyaviy ma’rifat ahamiyati haqida shunday yozadi: «Tarix kitobi yozishning bir sharti bor. Tarixiy voqealarni yozishda tarafdorlik etmasdan, bo’lgan hodisalarni rostlik bilan bayon etishi kerak. Agar rasmiylik bilan bayon etmasa, uning so’zlari hech bir odamga ma’qul bo’lmaydi». Bayoniy shularga amal qilib ikkita tarixiy asar «Xorazm tarixi» va «Shajarayi Xorazmshohiy»larni yozdi.

Haqiqatdan ham Bayoniy o’z davrining haqiqiy muharri bo’lib, Xiva xonligining chor Rossiyasi bosib olinishi va talon-taroj etilishini atroflicha sodda xalq tilida yozib bera olgan yirik tarixchi darajasiga ko’tariladi. Muhammad Solih domla Rahim Qoraxo’ja o’g’li. Toshkentli yirik tarixchi. U 1830-yil tug’ilgan. 1840-yildan 1863-yilgacha Toshkent, Qo’qon, Buxoroning nufuzli madrasalarida ta’lim olgan, arab, fors tillarini mukammal bilgan. Tarixchi olim Muhammad Solih o’lkani tarixini o’rganishda 25 yildan ortiq vaqt sarfladi. Nihoyat 1863-1888-yilgacha izlanishlar samarasi sifatida uning «Tarixi jadidayi Toshkent» (Toshkentning yangi tarixi) deb atalgan va ikki jilddan iborat kitobi yozilgan. Birinchidan jildda qadim zamonlardan to XV asr oxirigacha Sharq mamlakatlarida, shuningdek O’rta Osiyoda bo’lib o’tgan voqealar, ikkinchi jildda esa Farg’onaning XV asr oxiridan to XIX asrning 80-yillarigacha bo’lgan ijtimoiy siyosiy tarixi bayon etiladi. Asarning ilmiyligi shundaki, Toshkent shahri va viloyatiga doir tarixiy, jug’rofiy ma’lumotlar atroflicha, izchillikda berilib, Toshkentning XIX asr qiyofasi shu asar orqali mukammal yozildi. Shaharning devor va qo’rg’onlari, ularning orasidagi masofa, toponimik ma’lumotlar, shaharning 12 darvozasi, dahalari, masjid-madrasalari, hammomlari, bozorlari, hunarmandchilik sohalari, qishloq xo’jalik, qabriston va maqbaralari, suv ta’minot shahobchalari, bog’lar, mevayu-sabzavotlar, ekin-tekinlari siyosiy tarzda bayon qilingan.

Maxsus missiya bilan Turkistondagi temir yo’l qurilishini o’rganish uchun yuborilgan injener E. Bulanje (Edgar Boulanger, 1850–1899)ning hisobotlari “Sibirga sayohat xotiralari. Transsibir temir yo’li va Xitoy” nomli nashrida aks ettirilib, fransuz yozuvchisi Jyul Vern o’z asarlarida ulardan foydalangan.

Xyugges Kraftning “Rus Turkistoni bo’ylab” nomli asari 1902-yilda yozilgan bo’lib, unda Samarqand, Buxoro, Marg’ilon shaharlari, ulardagi bozorlar, do’konlar, choyxona, xiyobonlar, hunarmandchilik ustaxonalari, Samarqandning yirik obidalari, o’lkaning tog’ va landshafti, aholining turmush-tarzi, axloqi, ko’rinishi va kiyimlari, musulmonlarning yirik bayramlari kabi masalalarda qiziqarli ma’lumotlar beriladi.

Bulardan tashqari asarda juda ko’plab (200 dan ortiq) fotosuratlar keltirilgan. O’zbekiston Markaziy davlat arxividagi Turkiston general-gubernatori jamg’armasida o’sha davrda Turkistonga kelgan xorijiy sayyohlarning tashrifi bilan bog’liq ko’pgina hujjatlar mavjud.

Bu hujjatlarda sayyohlarga ruxsat berish, ularga o’lka shaharlarida va yo’llarda hamrohlik qilishi kabi masalalar bilan bog’liq rasmiy hujjatlar saqlangan.

Shuningdek, mahalliy ma'muriyat vakillariga sayyohlarni qabul qilish haqida ko'rsatmalar ham saqlangan.

Shunday tadqiqotchilardan biri vengriyalik mashhur sayyoh Arminiy Vamberi (1832-1913) o'zining Markaziy Osiyoga 1863-1864-yillarda uyushtirgan safari asosida yaratgan "Travels in Central Azia" ("Markaziy Osiyoga tashrif") nomli asari bilan dunyoga tanildi. U 1864-yilda yuqorida nomi keltirilgan asarini nashr etdi.

Deyarli barcha Yevropa tillariga shuningdek, rus tiliga tarjima qilingan mazkur asarda muallifning safar davomida Xiva, Buxoro hamda Qo'qon xonliklari hududida ko'rgan-kechirganlari, kuzatgan voqealari, mahalliy amaldor va mansabdorlar bilan suhbatlari, shaxsiy taassurotlari asosida ushbu hududlarning, ma'muriy-hududiy tuzilishi, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy infratuzilmasi, qurolli kuchlari, soliq va sud tizimi, qishloq xo'jaligi, aholisi va uning etnik tarkibi, shaharlari haqida qiziqarli va muhim ma'lumotlar qayd etiladi.

Asarda ayrim atamalar va tarixiy voqealar, joy nomlarida qator chalkashliklar, mahalliy xususiyatlar va mentalitetdan bexabarlik bois ba'zi masalalarga Yevropa voqeligidan kelib chiqqan holda yondashish holatlari yaqqol namoyon bo'lsa-da, ushbu asar hanuzgacha tarixiy manba sifatida o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan.

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